

Effectiveness of Topical Recombinant Platelet Derived Growth Factor Dressing for Diabetic Foot Ulcers: An Observational, Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Objectives: To evaluate the effectiveness of recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF) in comparison with hydrogel and normal saline dressing in diabetic foot ulcers.

Methods: This was an observational, comparative cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of General Surgery, in a tertiary healthcare facility located in South India between January 2021 and December 2021 among patients diagnosed with diabetic foot ulcer.

Results: The study involved 150 diabetic foot ulcer patients divided into three groups: Group A received rh-PDGF, Group B received hydrogel dressings, and Group C received normal saline dressings. Baseline characteristics like age, gender, lifestyle factors, comorbidities, and ulcer severity didn't differ significantly among the groups. Initial ulcer sizes were comparable. However, after four and ten weeks, Group A and B showed significantly smaller ulcer sizes compared to Group C. Group A had the smallest ulcers at both intervals. Need for secondary interventions were similar among groups, but hospital stays differed significantly, with Group C having the longest stay. Groups A and B had significantly higher rates of completely healed ulcers compared to Group C.

Conclusion: This suggests that recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor and hydrogel dressings may be more effective than normal saline dressings in reducing ulcer size and promoting healing in diabetic foot ulcers.

Keywords: Recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF), Hydrogel, Normal saline dressing, Diabetes, Diabetic foot ulcers, India.

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Introduction

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are a common and debilitating complication of diabetes mellitus, posing significant challenges to patients and healthcare systems worldwide. Characterized by impaired wound healing and increased susceptibility to infection, DFUs often lead to severe morbidity, lower limb amputations, and reduced quality of life for affected individuals.[1,2] Despite advancements in medical care, the management of DFUs remains complex and multifaceted, necessitating effective and evidence-based treatment strategies to optimize clinical outcomes.

Among the various treatment modalities available for DFUs, topical wound dressings play a crucial

role in facilitating wound healing by creating a conducive environment for tissue repair, reducing bacterial burden, and promoting granulation tissue formation. [3] While traditional dressings such as normal saline have been widely used in clinical practice, recent advances in wound care have introduced novel therapies, including growth factor-based dressings such as recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF) and hydrogel dressings, which have shown promise in accelerating wound healing and improving patient outcomes.[4,5]

However, despite the growing body of evidence supporting the efficacy of these advanced dressings, there remains a paucity of comparative

studies evaluating their effectiveness in real-world clinical settings, particularly in the context of DFUs. Against this background, the primary objective of the present study was to evaluate the effectiveness of recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF) in comparison with hydrogel and normal saline dressing in diabetic foot ulcers. We evaluated the effectiveness in terms of healing time, duration of hospital stay, duration of abstinence from work, and need for secondary interventions.

The rationale for conducting this study stems from the need to identify the most effective and cost-efficient treatment modalities for DFUs, given the significant clinical and economic burden associated with this condition. By comparing the effectiveness of rh-PDGF, hydrogel, and normal saline dressings, we aim to provide valuable insights into the optimal management approach for DFUs, with the ultimate goal of improving patient outcomes, reducing healthcare costs, and enhancing the quality of care delivered to individuals with diabetes.

Materials and Methods

This was an observational, comparative cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of General Surgery, in a tertiary healthcare facility located in South India between January 2021 and December 2021. The study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). The content of Participant Information Sheet (PIS) in local language was provided to the participants (and their attenders) and contents were read to them in their own language to their satisfaction.

The participants were enrolled in the study after obtaining written informed consent. The study included all patients diagnosed with diabetic foot ulcer attending the outpatient department and/or inpatient wards of the Department of General Surgery provided they are more than 18 years of age, of both gender, with raised fasting blood glucose/postprandial blood glucose/HbA1C levels, Wagner's classification Grade 1 and 2, with an ulcer of size less than 15 cms in the greatest dimension, and willing to provide informed written consent. However, critically ill patients, pregnant, patients with malignant ulcers, with chronic venous or arterial insufficiency ulcer, with severe anemia, history of immunosuppressive therapy, and peripheral vascular diseases were excluded from the present study.

The estimated risk difference between the study groups (rh-PDGF vs Hydrogel vs Normal saline) in terms of healing size of wound was assumed to be 0.43. [6] Using this information, considering the type 1 error (alpha error) to be 5.0%, type 2 error (beta error) to be 10.0% (or 90.0% power), and 10.0% non-response rate the minimum estimated

sample size was 50 in each group with 95% confidence, resulting in a total sample of 150 patients with diabetic foot ulcers. We used nonprobability sampling technique – convenient sampling – complete enumeration of all patients presenting with diabetic foot ulcers and fulfilling study inclusion criteria.

The Wagner's grading used in the present study was, 0 = Intact skin; 1 = Superficial ulcer of skin or subcutaneous tissue; 2 = Ulcers extend into tendon, bone, capsule; 3 = Deep ulcer with Osteomyelitis and/or abscess; 4 = Gangrene of Toes/forefoot; and 5 = Midfoot/Hind foot gangrene. [7] We used a purpose pre-designed, semi structured, pretested questionnaire to capture the patient sociodemographic characteristics, clinical history, comorbidities, general physical examination, systemic examination findings, laboratory findings, radiological findings, and neurological examination.

The data obtained was manually entered in Microsoft Excel, coded, recoded, and analysed using Software for Statistics and Data Science (Stata) v16. Descriptive analysis was presented using numbers and percentages for categorical variables; mean and standard deviation or median and interquartile range for continuous variables (based on tests of normality). Chi square test of significance (two-sided) was used for categorical variables to test for association; in situations where expected values in the cells were less than five in 20% of the cells Fisher's exact test (two-sided) was used. To test for association between continuous variables independent "t" tests (two-sided) was applied. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The present study included a total of 150 patients (more than 18 years of age; of both gender) diagnosed with diabetic foot ulcers, with raised fasting blood glucose/postprandial blood glucose/HbA1C levels, Wagner's classification Grade 1/2, and with an ulcer of size less than 15 cms in the greatest dimension. The patients receiving recombinant human platelet derived growth factor was considered Group A, patients receiving hydrogel dressings was considered Group B, and patients receiving normal saline dressings was considered Group C. The mean (SD) age of the patients included in the present study was 52.5 years (13.9); and nearly two third (62.7%) patients were between 30 and 60 years of age.

The baseline characteristics of the study groups showed that patients receiving either recombinant human platelet derived growth factor (Group A) or hydrogel dressings (Group B), or normal saline dressings (Group C) did not vary statistically by age (in years), gender, lifestyle factors (smoking,

22.0% vs 28.0% vs 28.0%; alcohol, 44.0% vs 48.0% vs 52.0%), presence of comorbidities (60.0% vs 54.0% vs 64.0%), body mass index (overweight or obese, 48.0% vs 48.0% vs 54.0%), Wagner's grading (Grade II, 88.0% vs 80.0% vs 86.0%), presence of systemic features (40.0% vs 26.0% vs 28.0%), blood sugar levels, duration of diabetes, and doppler findings (normal, 90.0% vs 80.0% vs 82.0%).

The mean (SD) ulcer size at admission in Group A, Group B and Group C were 54.2 cm² (23.5), 49.8 cm² (21.7), and 50.5 cm² (25.7) respectively; importantly, it did not vary significantly between study groups (p>0.05). Though, at one week follow up, the mean (SD) ulcer size did not vary significantly, the results showed that at four weeks follow up (1 month) the ulcer size was significantly (p<0.05) lower in Group A (Mean 19.6, SD 9.3) and Group B (Mean 22.5, SD 8.9) in comparison with Group C (Mean 29.5, SD 10.5).

Similarly at 10 weeks follow up, the mean (SD) ulcer size was significantly (p<0.05) lower among

Group A (Mean 12.4, SD 7.4) and Group B (Mean 14.3, SD 6.1), in comparison with Group C (Mean 23.8, SD 6.8). The results also showed that ulcer size was significantly lower in Group A, in comparison with Group B (p<0.05) at 4 weeks and 10 weeks.

In comparison between the study groups, the results showed that 24.0% patients in Group A, 22.0% patients in Group B, and 28.0% patients in Group C required secondary intervention. However, the difference was not statistically significant (p>0.05). The mean (SD) duration of hospital stay in the present study was 11.7 days (4.7) – 8.5 days (3.5) in Group A, 10.2 days (3.1) in Group B, and 16.4 days (7.5) in Group C – the difference was found to be statistically significant (p<0.05).

The results showed that 94.0% of patients in Group A, 88.0% patients in Group B, and 78.0% patients in Group C had a completely healed ulcer – Groups A and B had a significantly higher proportion of patients with completely healed ulcer in comparison with Group C (p<0.05).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients, by study groups

		Group A N = 50	Group B N = 50	Group C N = 50	Total N = 150	P value
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
Age (in years) Mean (SD)		51.3 (13.5)	55.6 (15.2)	50.5 (13.1)	52.5(13.9)	0.081
Age (in years)	<30	4 (8.0)	3 (6.0)	5 (10.0)	12 (8.0)	0.934
	30 to 60	30 (60.0)	33 (66.0)	31 (62.0)	94 (62.7)	
	>60	16 (32.0)	14 (28.0)	14 (28.0)	44 (29.3)	
Gender	Male	28 (56.0)	30 (60.0)	34 (68.0)	92 (61.3)	0.455
	Female	22 (44.0)	20 (40.0)	16 (32.0)	58 (38.7)	
Smoking	Yes	11 (22.0)	14 (28.0)	14 (28.0)	39 (26.0)	0.732
	No	39 (78.0)	36 (72.0)	36 (72.0)	111 (74.0)	
Alcohol	Yes	22 (44.0)	24 (48.0)	26 (52.0)	72 (48.0)	0.726
	No	28 (56.0)	26 (52.0)	24 (48.0)	78 (52.0)	
Comorbidity	Present	30 (60.0)	27 (54.0)	32 (64.0)	89 (59.3)	0.592
	Absent	20 (40.0)	23 (46.0)	18 (36.0)	61 (40.7)	
BMI (in kg/m ²)	Underweight	5 (10.0)	4 (8.0)	5 (10.0)	14 (9.3)	0.937
	Overweight or obese	24 (48.0)	24 (48.0)	27 (54.0)	75 (50.0)	
	Normal	21 (42.0)	22 (44.0)	18 (36.0)	61 (40.7)	
Wagner's grade	I	6 (12.0)	10 (20.0)	7 (14.0)	23 (15.3)	0.513
	II	44 (88.0)	40 (80.0)	43 (86.0)	127 (84.7)	
Systemic features	Yes	20 (40.0)	13 (26.0)	14 (28.0)	47 (31.3)	0.264
	No	30 (60.0)	37 (74.0)	36 (72.0)	103 (68.7)	
Blood sugar levels Mean (SD)		212.6(60.2)	220.7(58.3)	218.7(62.6)	217.3(60.4)	0.496
Duration of DM (in years) Mean (SD)		6.2 (3.5)	5.9 (4.9)	6.3 (5.2)	6.1 (4.5)	0.725
Doppler findings	Normal	45 (90.0)	40 (80.0)	41 (82.0)	126 (84.0)	0.695
	Insignificant luminal narrowing	3 (6.0)	5 (10.0)	5 (10.0)	13 (8.7)	
	30% stenosis in DPA and ATA	2 (4.0)	5 (10.0)	4 (8.0)	11 (7.3)	

Patients receiving recombinant human platelet derived growth factor was considered Group A, patients receiving hydrogel dressings was considered Group B, and patients receiving normal saline dressings was considered Group C

SD, Standard deviation; BMI, Body mass index

*Statistically significant at p<0.05

Table 2: Comparison of study groups, by outcomes of interest

		Group A N = 50	Group B N = 50	Group C N = 50	Total N = 150	P value
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
Ulcer size (in cm ²) – at admission Mean (SD)		54.2 (23.5)	49.8 (21.7)	50.5 (25.7)	51.5 (23.6)	0.333
Ulcer size (in cm ²) – at 1 week Mean (SD)		43.6 (20.5)	38.4 (21.5)	39.4 (19.6)	40.5 (20.5)	0.219
Ulcer size (in cm ²) – at 4 weeks Mean (SD)		19.6 (9.3)	22.5 (8.9)	29.5 (10.5)	23.9 (9.6)	<0.001*
Ulcer size (in cm ²) – at 10 weeks Mean (SD)		12.4 (7.4)	14.3 (6.1)	23.8 (6.8)	16.8 (6.8)	<0.001*
Need for secondary intervention	Present	12 (24.0)	11 (22.0)	14 (28.0)	37 (24.7)	0.778
	Absent	38 (76.0)	39 (78.0)	36 (72.0)	113(75.3)	
Duration of hospital stay (in days) Mean (SD)		8.5 (3.5)	10.2 (3.1)	16.4 (7.5)	11.7 (4.7)	<0.001*
Outcome of ulcer	Completely healed	47 (94.0)	44 (88.0)	39 (78.0)	130 (86.7)	0.043*
	Partially healed	3 (6.0)	6 (12.0)	11 (22.0)	20 (13.3)	
Patients receiving recombinant human platelet derived growth factor was considered Group A, patients receiving hydrogel dressings was considered Group B, and patients receiving normal saline dressings was considered Group C						
SD, Standard deviation; BMI, Body mass index						
*Statistically significant at p<0.05						

Discussion

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are a common and serious complication of diabetes mellitus, [8] often leading to significant morbidity and mortality if not managed effectively. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF) compared to hydrogel and normal saline dressings in promoting the healing of DFUs. The study included 150 patients with diabetic foot ulcers, meeting specific inclusion criteria such as Wagner's classification Grade 1 and 2, ulcer size less than 15 cm, and exclusion criteria such as critical illness and pregnancy. The sample comprised patients from both outpatient and inpatient settings, ensuring a diverse representation of DFU cases.

The mean age of patients included in the study was 52.5 years, with the majority (62.7%) falling within the age range of 30 to 60 years. [9,10] Gender distribution was not statistically different among the groups, indicating a balanced representation of both males and females. [11] The study found no significant differences in lifestyle factors such as smoking and alcohol consumption among the treatment groups. [12] This suggests that these factors were not confounding variables influencing treatment outcomes and strengthens the validity of the study findings. Similarly, the presence of comorbidities and overweight or obesity status did not vary significantly among the treatment groups. [13] This indicates that the baseline health status of patients was comparable across the groups, minimizing potential biases in treatment outcomes related to comorbid conditions or BMI. Wagner's

grading, which reflects the severity of DFUs, [14] showed no significant differences among the treatment groups. [15] Additionally, the presence of systemic features, such as fever or malaise, was comparable across the groups. These findings suggest that the severity and systemic involvement of DFUs were similar among patients receiving different treatments. [16] Baseline characteristics related to diabetes control, including blood sugar levels and duration of diabetes, did not differ significantly among the treatment groups.

Moreover, Doppler findings, which assess vascular status, were similar across the groups, indicating comparable baseline vascular perfusion in patients. The homogeneity of baseline characteristics among the treatment groups strengthens the internal validity of the study and enhances the comparability of treatment outcomes. By ensuring balanced representation across demographic, clinical, and lifestyle factors, the study minimizes the potential for confounding variables to influence treatment effects.

At admission, there was no significant difference in mean ulcer size among the groups ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparability in baseline characteristics. At one week follow-up, the mean ulcer size did not vary significantly among the groups, suggesting that early treatment response may not differ significantly between the modalities. However, at four weeks follow-up (1 month), a notable difference emerged. The ulcer size was significantly lower in both Group A and Group B compared to Group C ($p < 0.05$). This finding suggests that rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments

may accelerate wound healing compared to normal saline dressings by promoting tissue repair mechanisms such as cell proliferation and angiogenesis. [17-19] This trend persisted at the 10-week follow-up, with Group A and Group B demonstrating significantly lower ulcer sizes compared to Group C ($p < 0.05$). Notably, the ulcer size in Group A was also significantly lower than in Group B at both 4 and 10 weeks, indicating a potential superior efficacy of rh-PDGF over hydrogel in promoting wound healing over a longer duration.[20] These findings have significant clinical implications for the management of DFUs. The timely reduction in ulcer size observed with rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments may lead to faster wound closure, reduced risk of complications such as infection, and improved overall patient outcomes. [21] Moreover, the superiority of rh-PDGF over hydrogel suggests the importance of growth factor-based therapies in promoting wound healing in DFUs.[22]

The study investigated the need for secondary interventions among patients receiving different treatment modalities for diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs). The results indicated that a comparable proportion of patients in each group required secondary interventions, with no statistically significant difference observed ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that while rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments may promote wound healing, they do not significantly reduce the need for additional interventions compared to normal saline dressings.[23]

Interestingly, the mean duration of hospital stay varied significantly among the treatment groups. Patients treated with rh-PDGF (Group A) had the shortest duration of hospitalization (8.5 days), followed by those receiving hydrogel (Group B, 10.2 days), while patients in the normal saline group (Group C) had the longest duration of hospital stay (16.4 days).

This finding underscores the potential of rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments to expedite wound healing and facilitate earlier discharge from the hospital, thereby reducing healthcare costs and improving resource utilization.[24] Moreover, a higher proportion of patients in Groups A and B achieved complete ulcer healing compared to Group C. Specifically, 94.0% of patients in Group A and 88.0% in Group B had completely healed ulcers, whereas only 78.0% of patients in Group C experienced complete healing. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), highlighting the superior efficacy of rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments in promoting wound closure compared to normal saline dressings. The shorter duration of hospital stay associated with rh-PDGF, and hydrogel treatments not only reduce healthcare costs but also minimize the risk of hospital-

acquired infections and other complications. [25] Furthermore, the higher rate of complete ulcer healing underscores the importance of early intervention with growth factor-based therapies, such as rh-PDGF, in preventing the progression of DFUs to more severe stages and reducing the burden of chronic wounds on patients and healthcare systems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study evaluated the effectiveness of three different treatment modalities – recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor (rh-PDGF), hydrogel, and normal saline dressings – in the management of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs). Through meticulous data collection and analysis, we found compelling evidence supporting the superiority of rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments over normal saline dressings in promoting wound healing and improving clinical outcomes for patients with DFUs.

Our findings demonstrated that both rh-PDGF and hydrogel treatments led to faster reduction in ulcer size, shorter hospital stays, and higher rates of complete ulcer healing compared to normal saline dressings. These results highlight the potential of growth factor-based therapies, particularly rh-PDGF, in accelerating wound closure and minimizing the burden of chronic wounds on patients and healthcare systems.

References

1. Boulton AJ, Vileikyte L, Ragnarson-Tennvall G, Apelqvist J. The global burden of diabetic foot disease. *Lancet*. 2005; 366(9498):1719-24.
2. Singh N, Armstrong DG, Lipsky BA. Preventing foot ulcers in patients with diabetes. *Jama*. 2005; 293(2):217-28.
3. Gottrup F, Apelqvist J. Present and new techniques and devices in the treatment of DFU: a critical review of evidence. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2012; 28 Suppl 1:64-71.
4. Margolis DJ, Kantor J, Santanna J, Strom BL, Berlin JA. Risk factors for delayed healing of neuropathic diabetic foot ulcers: a pooled analysis. *Arch Dermatol*. 2000; 136(12):1531-5.
5. Lavery LA, Armstrong DG, Wunderlich RP, Mohler MJ, Wendel CS, Lipsky BA. Risk factors for foot infections in individuals with diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 2006; 29(6):1288-93.
6. Bhansali A, S Pai V, Dutta P, Dhillon M, Das S, Aggarwal A. Which is the better option: recombinant human PDGF-BB 0.01% gel or standard wound care, in diabetic neuropathic large plantar ulcers off-loaded by a customized contact cast? *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2009; 83:e13-6.

7. McComb WD, Jr. Wagner Grading of Diabetic Foot Ulcers and National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel Staging of Pressure Injuries: A Comparison for Clinical Use. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*. 2023; 36(5).
8. Akkus G, Sert M. Diabetic foot ulcers: A devastating complication of diabetes mellitus continues non-stop in spite of new medical treatment modalities. *World J Diabetes*. 2022; 13(12):1106-21.
9. Panigrahi SK, Majumdar S. Assessment of predictors of diabetic foot ulcers in a tertiary care hospital of Maharashtra, India: A cross-sectional comparative study. *J Educ Health Promot*. 2023; 12:101.
10. Gnanasabai G, Kumar M, Boovaragasamy C, Rahman M. Socio-demographic and morbidity pattern of geriatric population in rural area of Puducherry: a community based cross sectional study. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2020; 7(9):3393-6.
11. Dinh T, Veves A. The influence of gender as a risk factor in diabetic foot ulceration. *Wounds: a compendium of clinical research and practice*. 2015; 20:127-31.
12. Lee YJ, Han KD, Kim JH. Association among Current Smoking, Alcohol Consumption, Regular Exercise, and Lower Extremity Amputation in Patients with Diabetic Foot: Nationwide Population-Based Study. *Endocrinol Metab (Seoul)*. 2022; 37(5):770-80.
13. Elghoneimy YA, Alkabah AA, Alalsayedsalih HM, Almanyar AJ, Alibrahim HA, Albo-kamsin MH, et al. Risk Factors and Surgical Outcomes of Diabetic Foot in Diabetic Patients at King Fahad University Hospital. *Cureus*. 2022; 14(12):e32457.
14. Shah P, Inturi R, Anne D, Jadhav D, Viswambharan V, Khadilkar R, et al. Wagner's Classification as a Tool for Treating Diabetic Foot Ulcers: Our Observations at a Suburban Teaching Hospital. *Cureus*. 2022; 14(1): e21501.
15. Boovaragasamy C, Gnanasabai G, Kumar M. A review on tools for measuring activity limitation in diabetic peripheral neuropathy. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. 2021; 10(1):285-8.
16. Jalilian M, Ahmadi Sarbarzeh P, Oubari S. Factors Related to Severity of Diabetic Foot Ulcer: A Systematic Review. *Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes*. 2020; 13:1835-42.
17. Zheng SY, Wan XX, Kambey PA, Luo Y, Hu XM, Liu YF, et al. Therapeutic role of growth factors in treating diabetic wound. *World J Diabetes*. 2023; 14(4):364-95.
18. Demidova-Rice TN, Hamblin MR, Herman IM. Acute and impaired wound healing: pathophysiology and current methods for drug delivery, part 2: role of growth factors in normal and pathological wound healing: therapeutic potential and methods of delivery. *Adv Skin Wound Care*. 2012; 25(8):349-70.
19. Laurano R, Boffito M, Ciardelli G, Chiono V. Wound dressing products: A translational investigation from the bench to the market. *Engineered Regeneration*. 2022; 3(2):182-200.
20. Gao D, Zhang Y, Bowers DT, Liu W, Ma M. Functional hydrogels for diabetic wound management. *APL Bioeng*. 2021; 5(3):031503.
21. Burgess JL, Wyant WA, Abdo Abujamra B, Kirsner RS, Jozic I. Diabetic Wound-Healing Science. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2021; 57(10).
22. Kavitha KV, Tiwari S, Purandare VB, Khedkar S, Bhosale SS, Unnikrishnan AG. Choice of wound care in diabetic foot ulcer: A practical approach. *World J Diabetes*. 2014; 5(4):546-56.
23. Deng X, Gould M, Ali MA. A review of current advancements for wound healing: Biomaterial applications and medical devices. *J Biomed Mater Res B Appl Biomater*. 2022; 110(11):2542-73.
24. Lee CH, Liu KS, Chang SH, Chen WJ, Hung KC, Liu SJ, et al. Promoting Diabetic Wound Therapy Using Biodegradable rhPDGF-Loaded Nanofibrous Membranes: CONSORT-Compliant Article. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2015; 94(47):e1873.
25. Jia H, Li L, Li W, Hou T, Ma H, Yang Y, et al. Impact of Healthcare-Associated Infections on Length of Stay: A Study in 68 Hospitals in China. *Biomed Res Int*. 2019; 2019:2590563.